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INDIGENOUS PEOPLE'S ECONOMIC CRISIS AND MIGRATION: AN EYE-OPENING JOURNEY INTO TRIBAL UNHAPPY

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Abstract: *Prior to Covid-19, India's economic crisis, rising severance, low wages, and hazardous working conditions grew. On the other hand, the lockdown has made the migrants' living conditions even worse as a result of the pandemic. The government asked the people and used every means in its power to maintain "Social Distancing," but it has socially distanced itself from the poor and the underprivileged as a result of the widespread problem and measures taken to protect against it. These casual, unprotected workers face a number of current vulnerabilities, including a lack of social security, the fear of being laid off, a loss of income, and no prospect for rehabilitation or restoration. The problem suddenly dispersed the poor migrants, who were terrified and had no idea where to go because going back would only result in emptiness. Racial suffer from all aspects because they are the indigenous people who currently make up India's enormous migrant population. It raises a significant concern: Government strategies for dealing with the virus and these dispersed populations have been made more difficult by the sudden visibility of these migrant workers in Covid-19. The paper has attempted to investigate the conditions of racial and the consequences of tribal migrants migrating due to the constant circumstances that compel them to migrate and the threat of Covid-19 to meet and fight.*

Keywords: *Racial, Covid-19, migration, poverty.*

INTRODUCTION

Relocation has a long history of human development from one's starting point to another objective for human turn of events and better job. Human relocation has its patterns for various gatherings. Other reasons include migration for better opportunities and standardization of living conditions, whether forced or voluntary, as well as poverty, landlessness, debt, displacement, industrialization, the mining industry, and the fabrication that the goal of development is to effect change. Nevertheless, although all forms of change do not relate to development, they may disadvantage and deprive certain human communities. When dispossession results in a significant loss of land and property to the aforementioned community, such denial lowers their standard of living and puts their very existence in jeopardy. This negative perspective of negative inclusion leads to social exclusion, with no means and merciless ends. At the point when there is no food, land, or life in their place of creativity, they were pushed to relocate to an obscure area, with trust, may it feed them and give cover and treasure them as a being, however reality is by all accounts a bad dream. It is the government's responsibility to look out for such a vulnerable and

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deprived segment of society as people from diverse backgrounds migrate to big cities and urban areas in search of employment and better living conditions. In order to restore employment and safeguard the health, rights, and incomes of migrants working in the informal sector's workers as well as their families, government development plans, policy reforms, and economic assistance strategies require the proper establishment and implementation of such allocations. Migrants have little prior experience in their temporary home environment. They are experiencing a variety of social, psychological, and emotional difficulties as a result of concerns about their families' well-being and safety as well as a fear of being neglected by the community. Forced to leave their home countries in search of better opportunities and income, migrants frequently abandon their families and are trolled into an unknown future. The family behind them is entirely or partially dependent on the money that the migrants sent for them to eat and survive each day. The restrictions placed on routine activities as part of social distancing norms to prevent the spread of the infectious disease, COVID-19, halted these migrants' earnings and forced them to relocate back to their native communities. For a vast nation like India, where differences and discrimination permeate every facet of life, the study of human migration from one place to another reveals the truth, while every facet of life is marked by differences and discrimination. According to the World Economic Forum, the total number of Internal Migrants in the country, which was found in the 2011 Census and was staggering at 139 million, should not be overlooked or separated from the mainstream concepts of "development" and "relief." According to the 2017 Economic Survey of India, interstate migration in India reached a record high of close to 9 million per year between 2011 and 2016. In point of fact, population research must incorporate human migration for a variety of social, economic, or political reasons.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

IMPACTS OF THE LOCKDOWN AND COVID-19 SITUATION: HUMAN RIGHTS

In such pandemic situations, major ethical decisions and important plans have been made to protect all human dignity and human rights, regardless of any discrimination that is found among societal prejudices. In order to prevent bias, all social, economic, health, and medical benefits must approve any upheld government decisions and programs. It reaffirms the fundamental link between human rights, solidarity, and responsibility, which is essential in addressing the current crisis, and leads to the protection of privacy with the consent of the common masses. Preventative measures taken to restrict public transportation. Fixing area of interest regions/regulation zones need to control the spread of the pandemic, expanded and severe lockdowns of the whole populace with insufficient preparation. The human rights of a large portion of society have been severely impacted by inadequate protections for the most marginalized. These include violations of their rights to food, health, adequate housing, participation, and most importantly, to live in dignity. The most severely affected by the lockdown lost their means of subsistence, primarily daily wage workers, such as homeless and landless individuals, migrant workers, agricultural laborers, fish workers, and others in the "informal sector." Loss of income, starvation, ill health, depression, deprivation, and an increase in the number of malnourished infants are all added stresses to

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the lives of the poor in both urban and rural areas following the lockdown. Domestic violence against women, child abuse, detrimental health, loneliness, psychological stress, disruption in children's education and social connectivity and sensitivity, loss of life other than the pandemic, suicide, starvation, exhaustion, and denial of medical assistance are additional apocalyptic situations that have increased during the lockdown. The lockdown has had a significant impact on the homeless, who have experienced high levels of mournfulness, mental illness, fear and uncertainty, separation, a lack of communication with family members, forced habitat relocation, significant cash loss, and an increase in health complaints that are not related to the corona virus. More minor migrants have been subjected to police brutality and have even been denied access to food distribution centers in cities, where the general populace lacks adequate shelter.

As has been widely reported, the sudden and prolonged lockdown has the greatest impact on migrant workers because of their low incomes, inadequate social security and labor protections, and living conditions. States were instructed to seal borders and prevent migrants from returning home on March 28, 2020. While the focal government, on 29 April and 1 May, gave orders allowing transient specialists to get back, the orders accompany critical provisos, including an absence of clearness for execution. Worst of all, as reported in states like Karnataka, individuals who have not had a source of income for forty days or more are being required to pay for their return airfare, frequently at rates that are inflated. In spite of the lockdown and "stay at home" orders, forced evictions and home demolitions were reported in Jammu and Kashmir, Odisha, Rajasthan, and Telangana for a variety of reasons, leaving people homeless during the crisis. These evictions were cruel and severely violated a number of people's human rights, including their right to health and housing. People who are displaced, children who live on the streets, people with disabilities, older people, indigenous/tribal and other local communities who live in remote areas, single women, and so on are among the marginalized and vulnerable groups. Have not been harmed by the lockdown and have benefited from the majority of the relief measures. Disturbing incidents of assaults on workers, healthcare providers, and minorities have been reported in various regions.

COVID-19 AND SITUATION OF THE LABOUR MIGRANTS

The corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic has brought about an unprecedented global crisis in all spheres of individuals' lives, groups, and communities as a whole. Living in marginalized and vulnerable conditions has increased the risk, and their inability to cope with any positive measures to preserve their families and lives has been compounded by complete lockdowns, forced isolation, and quarantines. India gave the nation only four hours' notice when it announced a 21-day lockdown on March 24, 2020, as a response to halting the spread of COVID-19. The lockdown was extended for an additional 19 days, until 3 May 2020, on April 14, 2020. The lockdown was extended for two weeks on May 1, albeit with some relief divided into "green" and "orange" zones. The actual difficulties faced by the Indian population primarily increased the number of people living below the poverty line. Millions of migrants, who are the most vulnerable to COVID-19 and have migrated to India for 70 years, have endured immense suffering as a result. In Bihar, Jharkhand, and Odisha, nearly 90% of the cases that have been reported are migrants returning home.

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Due to this pandemic and lockdown, approximately 118 million poor migrants' jobs have been lost in the past, leading to massive socioeconomic emergencies and reverse migration.

The impact of Covid-19 on the lives and livelihoods of approximately 40 million interstate migrants has been estimated by the World Bank. These travelers are the genuine donor and financial raisers of the 'Host urban communities', however they were not dealt with during this pandemic, with outrageous pain and disregarded food and safe house considered savaged on roads to be the main takeoff since Free India. The adage "Home is where the heart is" applies to these migrants, who are marginalized farmers who are landless, burdened by debt, displaced from their ancestral lands, poor, deprived, socially excluded, and removed from the scale of development. They are also in search of better means of subsistence due to a lack of food. Hunger and poverty are realities that do not respect boundaries or any potentially hazardous circumstances. These migrants leave behind their difficult lives and move into difficult circumstances. The unexpected declaration by the public authority for complete lockdown caused these powerless transient workers from every which way of India to footslog many kilometers back to their country, conveying their small possessions hauling their eager and parched kids in the scorching intensity. In the midst of the Corona virus outbreak, a nation questioned whether the difficult circumstances could have prevented workers from receiving adequate food and shelter in their host cities and places of employment. Because they were unable to pay the rent on single-room rented homes, these marginalized workers were forced to move out by their landlords. The poor laborers were forced to accept the pain and unbelievable walking distances of hundreds of kilometers because they were afraid they would starve to death. They had to choose between starvation, economic collapse, or pandemic death—the devil or the deep sea. Witnessing such a large-scale movement across the country without food or a place to sleep was nothing short of a nightmare for India; the government needed to be a good Samaritan at the time.

LEGALITY AND ADJUDICATORY CONCERNS ON TRIBAL RIGHTS (LAND, WATER AND FOREST)

ILO Show No. The International Treaty No. 169 was approved in 1989 by the International Labor Organization (ILO). It was created to represent the rights of indigenous peoples and tribal peoples within the nation-states, as well as the responsibilities of governments to preserve their culture, land, and natural resources, as well as to establish their priorities for development. These priorities include employment and vocational training, education, health and social security, customary law, traditional institutions, languages, religious beliefs, and cross-border cooperation. More than 70 countries around the world are home to indigenous and tribal peoples, also known as Advises, mountain dwellers, hill tribes, and hunter-gatherers. These people make up about 5% of the world's population. The ILO adopted the Forced Labor Convention in 1930 as a direct result of the exploitation, differentiation, and discrimination of tribal workers and indigenous peoples. Later in the 1950s, these peoples' working conditions were seen as dangerous and critical because they were the result of deeply ingrained injustices and prejudices and fundamentally linked to larger issues of identity, language, culture, customs, and land. As a result, the ILO adopted the Indigenous and Tribal Populations Convention in 1957 on behalf of the UN system. The first international treaty to address indigenous peoples' rights was Convention. All research and statistics show that indigenous peoples still face the worst forms of labor exploitation and are unfairly represented

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among discrimination victims. Their rights to their land and natural resources are not recognized, and they are restricted in their shifting cultivation, pastoralism, hunting, and gathering practices. They are vulnerable and drawn toward exploitative practices like bonded labor, human trafficking, and even child labor due to widespread marginalization and poverty. In the labor market, Indigenous people face obstacles and disadvantages. Traditional knowledge and skills are not always valued or in demand, and they have limited access to education and vocational training. Lack strong ties to labor organizations and are ignorant and perplexed about their rights. The indigenous peoples' right to employment, vocational training, and protection of their labor rights are the subject of a whole section of the Convention. In addition, the fundamental labor conventions regarding non-discrimination, freedom from forced labor and child labor, freedom of association, and the right to collective bargaining are increasingly being used by the ILO and its constituents to address the situation of indigenous peoples.

Indigenous peoples face significant challenges in health and education, as well as significantly higher rates of poverty than other groups in most nations. Low public investments on indigenous lands, such as in communication and infrastructure, May also be a result of structural discrimination. In addition, because their production systems may be primarily focused on subsistence and they typically work in the informal sectors as unskilled laborers or domestic workers, indigenous peoples' contributions to the national economy and development frequently go unnoticed. The economic potential to end discrimination against indigenous peoples and to protect the economic and development perspectives of indigenous cultures, knowledge and production systems, and natural resources is becoming increasingly recognized. Indigenous people are aware of their entitlements to participation, consultation, and benefit sharing. To avoid conflicts and obligations to the state, the development process must be respected. Promoting democratic principles by requiring special consultation and participation in the decision-making process in scheduled areas. No. Convention 169 is a tool for good governance, conflict resolution, and bringing together a variety of interests. Indigenous peoples have the potential to become full partners in the development process if their rights and aspirations for the process are respected. This is a significant step toward national economies.

In general, the indigenous peoples are heavily reliant on the land and its natural resources for their income and survival. No. Convention In general, 169 state that indigenous peoples have the right "to participate in the use, management, and conservation of these resources" and "to the natural resources about their lands." In scheduled areas, the state typically retains ownership of minerals, subsurface resources, and other resources. The Convention sets up a number of safeguards to make sure that indigenous peoples are properly consulted get to enjoy the benefits, and get fair compensation for any harm they cause. The general conditions on consultation and participation that were detailed in the section before this one are applied in conjunction with the natural resources provisions. Before exploring and exploiting the natural resources that are located on their lands, the Convention emphasizes the necessity of determining the extent to which indigenous peoples' interests are prejudiced. Article underscores that the public authority should help out native people groups to evaluate arranged exercises' social, profound, social, and

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ecological elements. The consequences of these investigations will be viewed as key models for the execution of the exercises.

In addition, it is essential to keep in mind that the provisions pertaining to impact assessment and consultation apply to the actual exploitation of resources as well as the exploration phase. Conflicts arise between private sector actors who have obtained concessions or licenses from the state and indigenous peoples due to inadequate implementation of consultation, participation, and impact assessment. In this context, it is essential to emphasize that the state is responsible for ensuring the proper application of the right to consultation and participation. Because indigenous peoples may legitimately invoke their rights to be respected under the Convention, failure to comply with this responsibility will put the investments made by the private sector in jeopardy.

RACIAL SITUATION AND FAILED POLICIES: MIGRATION A COMPULSION

Racial, also known as forest dwellers or Indigenous peoples, are among the most disadvantaged members of society. Protecting the environment for a long time and earning a living on a sustainable basis, they live in discrete settlements on the outskirts of the mainstream of development, accustomed to their ancestral lands. Troublesome is the issue of tribal development. Legitimate courses of action to forestall distance of terrains held by the ancestral populace are problematic, as need might arise to be restored for lawful exchange with appropriate execution and further security of the financial incapacities of these poor ancestral populaces. The government has implemented developmental programs, affirmative policies, and laws to protect tribal people from this backwardness and development crisis. The nation's Scheduled Tribes' welfare, development, and preservation are protected by a number of constitutional provisions. In addition to the National Commission, the Central Indian States and the North-Eastern Region States provide the racial with the 5th and 6th Schedules for the purposes of protection and administrative administration.

"The Provision of Panchayats (Extension to the Scheduled Areas) Act, 1996, confers special powers on Gram sabha in Scheduled Areas to protect their land and forest from outside invasion and to participate in the decision-making process," in addition. The "Forest Rights Bill" and the "Land Rehabilitation & Resettlement Policy" are two additional provisions that give tribal people the authority to protect their land and forests. Even though these provisions of the Constitution are in place, they are not actually put into action. The genuine spirit that is produced by the state is an excellent impediment to the country's welfare and development strategy for these vulnerable groups. Due to their low socioeconomic status, poverty, severance, displacement, indebtedness, lack of opportunities, and even ignorance of government programs, tribal people in India face insurmountable consequences despite affirmative action. In addition, the most unfortunate consequence of globalization, liberalization, and privatization is that the government and private industry have blindly decided to establish massive mining, hydroelectric, industry, business, transportation, and road projects. This has resulted in the digging of holes in their ancestral land without their consent, resulting in the loss of traditional land ownership and opportunities

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for earning a living. The racial are no place put in the excursion of development and advancement rather pushed towards obliteration and failures.

In addition, this has caused a large number of rural tribal people to migrate to urban areas in search of work, either temporarily or permanently. This has disrupted their traditional socio-psychological family relationship, their network of neighborly relationships, and made it more difficult for them to adapt to the new urban culture. Large-scale internal migrations and labor mobility, in particular, have a long history together, and different flows have different durations, reasons, and migrant profiles that affect where families and communities go and where they come from. Specifically, human movement and its suggestions are turning into a significant financial issue for the policymakers and government to embrace government assistance and improvement exercises. In the poorest communities, internal, seasonal migrations serve as a "safety valve."

COVID-19 ENDANGERED THE LIVES OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLE: LOSS OF JOBS, HUNGER AND REVERSE MIGRATION

Because they are too closely associated with Mother Earth for food, water, shelter, and fuel, tribes are referred to as "Adivasis," "aboriginal peoples," and "forest dwellers." The Indian Constitution arrangements comprehensively; Protective measures, reservation and development, policies and affirmative action's for tribes, and affirmative action programs have all contributed to the majority of the tribal population's improved quality of life over the past six decades. Poor health, a lack of access to education, and the loss of social, cultural, and economic features of their ancestral societal history all contribute to tribal people's poverty. The tribal have moved toward a form of discourse living as a result of the mining industry's invasion, colonization, and exploitation of their lands, forests, and other resources. Due to their uniqueness of living in such a remote location, tribal areas are further removed from mainstream society as a result of being excluded from the source of development and receiving inadequate allocations. The state-supported improvement projects and plans connecting with their work and pay age exercises appear to be a simple endorsement because of ineffectual execution. As a result, they continue to be at the end of development. Losing land and their hereditary living spaces because of misleading commitments makes transient developments a superior type of revenue and endurance for their families. The tribal communities use seasonal migration as a "safety valve" to migrate and find the resources they need to survive elsewhere. Long-term migration follows seasonal migration. Among the tribal, forced migrations resulting from land alienation and complete dispossession, a growing number of migrating families, collective acceptance of lowering daily wages, and a growing vulnerability to contractors or corruption practices appear to be the essence of migration more frequently.

With some hope, thousands of indigenous people move to metropolitan cities as a result of industrialization, primarily to work in informal industries. The introduction of COVID-19 has destroyed the economy, leading to a lack of jobs, destroyed homes, and widespread hunger; these indigenous migrant workers are set to return, potentially bringing the diseases back to their communities. It has the potential to permanently damage the survival of numerous communities and wipe out endangered Indian

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indigenous peoples. Due to their low immunity and tradition of living in close-knit communities, these tribes are particularly susceptible to infectious diseases. Poverty rates among the Scheduled Tribes are higher than among the general population. The scheduled tribes live below the poverty line, according to the Ministry of Tribal Affairs, at 45.3% in rural areas and 24.1% in urban areas in 2011-12, compared to 25.7% in rural areas and 13.7% in urban areas overall. As a result, it is presumptuous that the tribal community is without a doubt the most adversely affected by the lockdown and the lack of attention paid by the local administration to providing essential facilities. The tribal population already suffers from hunger and malnutrition, but the current pandemic, restricted movement, and lack of other means of subsistence have exacerbated the problem. The Times of India reported on 2 April 2020 that approximately 70,000 Adivasi tea workers in the Barak Valley region of Assam have been working without pay or rations since 24 March 2020, making it difficult for them to eat a proper meal each day. The National Food Security Act, the National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme, rations under the Antodaya Scheme, and the Prime Minister's flagship health insurance program, Ayushman Bharat, all continued to deny benefits to racial who were reported to be starving. The Hindu reported on March 27, 2020, that more than 30,000 tribal laborers from the Madhya Pradesh district of Jhabua had returned from Gujarat, Rajasthan, and Maharashtra. On March 25, 2020, another Down To Earth report stated that thousands of tribal-primarily migrant workers had returned to their homes in Banswara, Dungarpur, Udaipur, and Sirohi in Rajasthan; Madhya Pradesh's Jhabua and Gujarat's tribal districts of Dahod, Panchmahals, Banaskantha, and Sabarkantha. In the absence of public transportation, the majority of them have walked hundreds of kilometers to get back. After screening, all migrant workers must self-isolate for 14 days in accordance with the COVID-19 protocol. However, because they didn't have enough space at home, many tribal migrants went back to where they came from. For instance, in the Purulia district in West Bengal, they had to spend the required 14 days alone outside the village, sleeping on trees, in trucks or buses, and in makeshift shelters.

CONSEQUENCES OF COVID-19 ON TRIBAL AND FOREST DWELLERS

REVERSE MIGRATION As a result of the lockdown, a significant portion of the poor and marginalized communities has experienced a significant migration. The racial have experienced a loss of their means of subsistence, physical challenges, a lack of food and shelter, and an increase in their economic distress. There are reports from all over the country of migrant workers experiencing severe hardships, a lack of food or other necessities for their communities, and a loss of income. Ancestral and other woodland staying networks are unavoidably getting impacted by Corona virus and the lockdown measures.

Lack of access to health benefits and insufficient information about the covirus 19 pandemic The Scheduled Areas are in remote locations where racial and forest dwellers are marginalized and unaware of the necessary measures to combat the pandemic. The health of these Indigenous people is in grave danger. They face an increased risk of both communicable and non-communicable diseases, as well as a lack of access to healthy living options and health benefits. Because of the lockdown, turn around relocation among the ancestral has raised the worry of spreading Corona virus disease in ancestral regions. Malnutrition, malaria, leprosy, and tuberculosis (TB) are just a few of the chronic diseases and

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health issues that the tribal population has experienced as a result of social deprivation. Due to the tribal population's weak immune system and traditional way of life, the lack of healthcare facilities can severely limit their ability to deal with COVID 19 outbreaks. This raises the risk of infection for the tribal population. The disease is only adequately tested and monitored in urban environments. In addition, there is a lack of pertinent information about infectious diseases and preventative measures in indigenous languages, making these tribal people even less able to deal with the issue.

Tribes are at risk of losing their jobs and running out of food as a result of the loss of their traditional lands and territories and forced migration, which already puts them at risk for food insecurity. When they return to their homelands, they will face even greater obstacles in getting food. Many Indigenous people who work in traditional occupations, subsistence economies, or the informal sector suffer from the loss of their traditional livelihoods, which frequently depend on land. The real supporter's situation is even worse for indigenous women, who provide food and nutrition to their families. Tribal migrants have observed that cardholders have limited access to the Public Distribution System. In a humanitarian context, extending the need to migrants is prioritized by ensuring that tribal people have access to food and adequate nutrition during the lockdown. Ration, vegetables, cooking oil, and other necessities must be readily available at the door. Service of Country Improvement has proactively written to state legislatures on direct money moves, extra annuities and so forth., as a temporary solution during the lockdown. However, in order to guarantee that all tribal people and OTFDs who are eligible receive their cash benefits, the Central Government ought to provide the State Government with sufficient financial resources. Additionally, tribal people and forest dwellers, according to reports, are unable to receive direct cash benefits because they do not have bank accounts or because banks are located far from their villages. It is noted that this is a problem with a lack of social security, particularly in terms of labor rights for migrant workers. Poorly implemented legislation includes the Unorganized Workers Social Security Act of 2008. These specialists without any means are removed from specific work privileges and put no liability on the business for their prosperity, especially in the ongoing setting. The state is responsible for making a serious effort to resume the implementation of MGNREGA, which would further facilitate land development and increase the productivity of Community Forest Resources, among other things. Racial are forest dwellers that are entirely dependent on forest products for food, shelter, and medicine. Minor forest products destruction to tribal livelihoods The lockdown has had a significant impact on the sale of minor forest products known as Non-Timber Forest Products (NTFPs), which are used to generate cash income by collecting and selling forest products on the market. The 60% yearly NTFP assortment season starts from April to June, turns out critical revenue to help ancestral, and, sadly, concurs unequivocally with the lockdown. Sincerely, the collection and sale of NTFPs are the primary occupations of the tribal women. Their families are affected by this season's unpredictability, which restricts the tribal's mobility due to the non-recognition of forest rights and security. NTFP collection has been made possible by guidelines in states like Maharashtra and Odisha. Even though the Minister, MoTA, addressed the NTFP issues in a letter to Chief Ministers and issued an order on April 16 exempting NTFP collection from lockdown, these measures do not fully address the MFP issues. The Base Help Cost conspire (MSP), a critical financial wellbeing net, has neglected to convey because of absence of execution in many states and cutting of

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least help costs of numerous NTFPs by the focal government. MoTA announced the revision of MSP for 49 MFPS in a letter to the conditions on May 1, 2020, after consulting with some states.

Most importantly, its compatibility with the FRA and PESA's Gram Sabha-centric forest governance mechanisms is unclear. In addition, the lockdown has completely disrupted NTFP trading and the value chain because traders are unwilling to purchase NTFPs in the current circumstance. Both the focal and state legislatures need to devise methodologies to draw in with the brokers to guarantee the acquisition of NTFPs. The income of communities that collect tend leaves has been further impacted by the introduction of GST.

Issues of PVTGs

Among the ancestral, the especially weak ancestral gatherings (PVTGs) are considerably more helpless. Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) in 18 States and Union Territories of Andaman & Nicobar Islands, the 75 PVTGs listed live in remote and dispersed areas of India. They all stay powerless, with poor regulatory and foundation reinforcement. Due to the loss of their traditional rights to cultivate and make use of forests as a means of subsistence, they have become more vulnerable over time. Hunger, starvation, malnutrition, etc., have resulted as a result. Resulting in a precarious situation for PVTG members' basic survival. The FRA's provisions regarding PVTGs' rights to tribal habitat have not been effectively implemented in the states. Their current struggle for survival has been made even more difficult by the lockdown measures. According to reports, they are unable to access forests in order to meet their basic needs. They also do not have access to any other means of earning a living. They have asked the Jharkhand government to implement a relief package for PVTGs that includes cash grants, soap, refined grains, pulses, vegetables, oil, and medicines. Due to the lack of protective masks in tribal areas, it has been reported that Gotti Koya and other tribal members in the Mulugu district of Telangana were wearing face masks made of teak leaves, that tribal members in the Bastar district of Chhattisgarh were using masks made of palm leaves to cover their faces, and that tribal members in the Vizianagaram district of Andhra Pradesh were wearing masks made of herbal leaves.

Afforestation and diverting forest land Despite the lockdown, the FRA still allows for the diverting of forest land without Gram Sabha's consent. Because it would result in forest destruction, displacement, and the loss of livelihoods, the local tribal have been resisting such a pursuit of forests. It involves worry that the MoEF has been clearing woodland and making a redirection as of now. When people are in lockdown and unable to leave even if they try to resist, they have issued new guidelines that relax forest and environmental clearance requirements for mining by new tenants.

There are reports of Compensatory Afforestation (CA) plantations being carried out on forest land used by tribal and other traditional forest dwellers, including by fencing such areas accessed for community rights, as COVID 19 spreads and livelihoods are affected by the lockdown. These activities are in direct infringement of their privileges under the FRA. By affecting the livelihoods of tribal and forest dwellers and destroying agro-biodiversity, they are currently causing severe distress. The forest department can

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now carry out forestry and plantation activities thanks to an order from the MoHA. The forest department may misuse this order to plantations on tribal and forest dwellers' land and community forest resources, thereby further violating their land and forest rights. In order to support local livelihoods and the agro ecology and biodiversity of the region, the MoTA must ensure that the guidelines allowing forestry operations and plantations are implemented only with the necessary safeguards to comply with the Forest Rights Act and with the consent of gram sabhas.

COVID-19 AND MINORITY RIGHTS: OVERVIEW AND SUGGESTED

PRACTICES AND Activities

In the Corona virus circumstance, the issues and methodologies for ancestral incorporates measures tended to by the Service of Ancestral Undertakings, as so;

1. As representatives, leaders, authorities, and the government must provide health services in response to Covid-19 in scheduled areas with its feedbacks, Indigenous peoples are vulnerable in approach. The Central Government must ensure that tribal areas have adequate testing and healthcare facilities, such as COVID Care Centers and mobile health units.
2. Because these Indigenous peoples have their own distinct culture and language, messages about hygiene, physical distance, quarantine, and prevention must be communicated in indigenous languages with the help of the general public. To prevent the virus that is relevant to their indigenous practices from spreading, it is difficult to provide and manage clean water, sanitation, and hygiene in such remote areas.
3. Alongside all availabilities, it's fundamental to bring mindfulness among them through the association of the native youth in the proclamation of Corona virus messages inside the networks to make things simpler and major to them to help their customary business.
4. Additionally, the Ministry of Tribal Affairs must collaborate with state governments, other tribal departments, and civil society to broadly monitor and support forest dwellers' needs. With the necessary availability of administrative proposals in tribal areas, the MoTA needs to be on the lookout and actively participating in its proceedings. Also, to get around the problems with district, sub-district, and state officials by giving states guidelines on what to do to help tribal and forest residents deal with COVID and lockdown.
5. To reach racial, PVTGs, and OTFDs, the MoTA needs the promotion and support of state-tribal departments. With the assistance of ASHA, ANM employees, and others, to raise awareness of COVID-19, provide protection measures, information about the nature of the disease, measures for quarantine and containment, testing, and dispelling vaccination myths, among other things, in the local language. Fundamentally, exceptional consideration ought to be given to regions with transient specialists who have gotten back, giving testing offices and quarantine illustrations, great veils, sanitizers and crises guaranteed by the neighborhood panchayats is a genuine assist them with receiving an immunization shot.

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6. There is evidence of undernourishment strategies in many tribal areas, despite the requirement for free food and ration distribution through PDS and basic income to support migrant workers and tribal and forest dwellers.

7. In addition to NTFP's purchase and sale of the products, the Gram Sabhas and the FRA-established forest management committees should receive direct financial and logistical support. The Forest Department ought to be instructed to extend NTFP transport. The MSP scheme's prices will rise as a result of this immediate action, which will also provide the tribal with much-needed income support during the lockdown. The central government should waive the GST on tendu leaves as concern support, which can significantly increase the income of tribal and forest residents.

8. To ensure food security and wage employment for tribal people and OTFDs under MGNREGA, the Ministry of Tribal Affairs should work with the Ministry of Resources Development (MoRD) and state development agencies to facilitate basic income-generating activities, including appropriate and adequate FRA policies for increasing productivity and land development. MoTA ought to empower MoEF to deliver the huge compensatory afforestation reserve accessible to the Gram Sabhas under comprised FRA to help ancestral local area woods the board for producing vocations and pay enrolment for racial and woodland inhabitants to accord with the monetary emergency. In order to avoid violating the forest rights of tribal and forest dwellers, MoEF ought to reevaluate its policy decisions made during the lockdown to facilitate environmental and forest clearances.

CONCLUSION

The Indian economy has been severely affected by COVID-19, and regaining such tranquility is uncertain and challenging. All groups of people have been primarily affected by job losses, rising severance, and underemployment structure. The unorganized sector and the poor and deteriorating migrants have sustained the majority of its damage. The tribal population's severance presents a problem for the government when they return to their ancestral homes. There was no longer a means of subsistence because of the mining and invasion of their homes. MGNREGA, the potential solution that has been underperforming for a variety of reasons since its inception, has already experienced a collapse in forest income-generating farm income. So giving specific reliefs through such projects is lacking activity of the public authority. Migration appears to be a glimmer of hope for those who risk their lives in cities and engage in perilous activities in order to at least earn enough money to meet their needs. However, as a result of this pandemic, they are once more pushed back without any source of income, which has made their lives and mental health worse. Since all of the interstate migrants have returned to their home countries, the hardest-hit need to be cared for and concerned about virus exposure and economic decline. The indigenous communities are left behind as a result of the crunch caused by inadequate funding, inadequate social services, and not being correctly listed in the government's developmental order. As a result, they are more helpless to deal with the pandemic. Information and communication in native languages are required, as are appropriate medical supplies, emergency sanitation supplies, emergency food, and financial assistance. COVID-19 is a challenge that must be fought vigorously and collectively by

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implementing determined and efficient measures to provide specific assistance to indigenous peoples through full consultation, participation, and culturally appropriate means, with the goal of enabling the most vulnerable segment of society in the future.

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